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Effect Of Domestic Violence On The Academic Performance Of Senior Secondary School Students In Port Harcourt Metropolis

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated effect of domestic violence on the academic performance of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Expos Facto research design was adopted for the study. The population of this study consists of 6802 senior secondary students in Port Harcourt metropolis, multi-stage sampling procedure was used to sample 378 students from the population using Taro Yemen formula. Out of 378 instruments distributed to the sampled teachers, 271 were properly filled and used for data analysis. Data were collected using three adapted instrument; Academic Performance Scale (APS), Physical Domestic Violence (PDVS) and Emotional Domestic Violence Scale (EDVS). The instruments were validated by experts from on text construction. Internal consistency of the instrument was determined through Cronbach Alpha statistics and reliability coefficients of 0.75, 0.68 and 0.89 was gotten showing that the instrument is reliable for the study. Simple regression analysis was used to answer all the research questions. t-test associated with simple regression was used to test the corresponding hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The result of this study reveals that physical domestic violence and emotional domestic violence significantly affects the academic performance of secondary school students.

Keywords: Physical Domestic Violence, Emotional Domestic Violence and Academic Performance

INTRODUCTION

Education is fundamental to the cognitive, emotional, and social development of adolescents and plays a crucial role in shaping future career prospects and social adjustment (Bentil, Dabone, & Boye, 2024). However, the effectiveness of educational processes is greatly influenced by the home environment in which students are raised. A supportive and peaceful home environment promotes learning, while exposure to violence within the family undermines students' academic and psychological development.

Academic performance refers to the extent to which a learner achieves educational objectives, usually measured through examinations, grades, standardized test scores, and continuous assessments. It reflects the level of knowledge, skills, and competencies acquired by students within a specific period of instruction. Academic performance is a central construct in educational research; it refers to the extent to which students achieve educational objectives, typically measured through examination scores, classroom participation, attendance, and completion of academic tasks. Academic performance is influenced by

individual factors such as motivation and intelligence, as well as environmental factors such as family stability, emotional well-being, and exposure to stressors (Bentil et al., 2024). York, Gibson, and Rankin (2019) conceptualize academic performance as measurable learning outcomes that indicate how well students meet curricular and institutional standards. Within formal school systems, academic performance is commonly operationalized through grades, cumulative grade point averages (CGPA), teacher evaluations, and standardized assessments, which serve as indicators of students' progress and achievement. Kuh et al. (2020) describe academic performance as institutionally defined indicators of student success, reflecting achievement, persistence, and progression within educational programs.

Domestic violence, which includes physical and emotional abuse among family members, has become a major social concern globally and in Nigeria. In many Nigerian homes, children are either direct victims of violence or witnesses to physical assaults and emotional abuse between parents or caregivers. Such exposure creates a climate of fear, insecurity, and emotional distress that interferes with learning processes (Williams, Oyundoyin, & Adeyemi, 2024). Domestic violence refers to a pattern of abusive behaviours used by one family member to exert power and control over another, including physical assault, emotional abuse, intimidation, and psychological manipulation (Lawal & Ishaq, 2025). For adolescents, domestic violence may involve direct victimisation or witnessing violent interactions between caregivers. Research indicates that such exposure has profound implications for emotional stability, cognitive development, and academic functioning (Williams et al., 2024).

A clear form of domestic violence is physical domestic violence. This involves acts such as hitting, beating, pushing, or any form of bodily harm within the home. Exposure to physical violence has been linked to trauma-related symptoms including fear, anxiety, sleep disturbances, and hypervigilance, all of which impair attention, memory, and problem-solving skills necessary for learning (Williams et al., 2024). Empirical studies in Nigeria and other African contexts reveal that students exposed to physical domestic violence exhibit higher levels of absenteeism, reduced classroom participation, and behavioural problems, which collectively contribute to poor academic performance (Lawal & Ishaq, 2025). The constant fear associated with violent home environments reduces students' motivation to learn and their ability to concentrate on academic tasks.

Emotional Domestic Violence (also called psychological or emotional abuse) refers to a pattern of non-physical behaviors used by one partner or family member to control, intimidate, manipulate, isolate, or undermine another person's sense of self-worth, emotional well-being, and autonomy within a domestic or intimate relationship. Scholars define emotional domestic violence as repeated acts of verbal aggression, humiliation, threats, coercion, manipulation, gaslighting, intimidation, isolation, and controlling behaviors that cause psychological harm and emotional distress to the victim (Dokkedahl et al., 2019). Unlike physical abuse, emotional domestic violence does not involve bodily harm, but it can be equally damaging due to its long-term effects on mental health and self-concept. According to World Health Organization (WHO)-aligned research, emotional domestic violence includes behaviors such as constant criticism, insults, belittling, threats of harm, restriction of social contacts, monitoring movements, and emotional neglect, all aimed at establishing power and control over the victim (Sardinha et al., 2022). These behaviors often occur alongside other forms of domestic violence but may also exist independently. From a psychological perspective, emotional domestic violence is defined as a systematic attempt to erode an individual's emotional stability, self-esteem, and personal identity through persistent emotional manipulation and psychological pressure (Archer & Graham-Kevan, 2020). Victims commonly experience anxiety, depression, low self-worth, fear, emotional dependency, and impaired social functioning. Furthermore, Emotional domestic violence includes verbal abuse, threats, humiliation, rejection, and constant criticism. Although it does not leave visible scars, emotional abuse has long-lasting psychological consequences for adolescents. Victims of emotional violence often experience low self-esteem, depression, anxiety, and social withdrawal, which negatively affect academic engagement (Bentil et al., 2024). Studies have shown that emotional distress resulting from domestic violence interferes with students' school attendance, participation, and persistence in academic tasks. Chronic

emotional abuse generates sustained stress that impairs executive functions such as attention control and working memory, leading to declining academic achievement (Williams et al., 2024).

This study is anchored on trauma theory which was traced to Sigmund Freud in the 20th century, which posits that exposure to traumatic experiences such as domestic violence disrupts normal emotional and cognitive development. Trauma theory explains that prolonged exposure to fear and stress alters brain functioning and emotional regulation, thereby impairing learning and academic performance (Bentil et al., 2024). In the school context, traumatised students often display concentration difficulties, emotional dysregulation, and behavioural challenges.

Persistent poor academic performance, absenteeism, lack of concentration, and behavioural challenges among senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Metropolis have raised serious concerns among educators and policymakers. While factors such as teaching quality, school facilities, and peer influence have been widely examined, the role of domestic violence as a contributing factor has received limited scholarly attention. Many students live in homes characterised by physical aggression, verbal abuse, intimidation, and emotional neglect. Exposure to such hostile environments often results in emotional trauma, anxiety, and psychological distress, which negatively affect students' ability to cope with academic demands (Lawal & Ishaq, 2025). Without adequate understanding of how physical and emotional domestic violence influence academic performance, interventions aimed at improving students' learning outcomes may remain ineffective. This study therefore seeks to investigate effect of domestic violence on academic performance of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt metropolis.

The following research question will be answered in this study

1. What is the effect of Physical domestic violence on academic performance of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Metropolis?
2. What is the effect of Emotional domestic violence on academic performance of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt metropolis?

The following hypotheses will be tested under 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant effect of Physical domestic violence on academic performance of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.
2. There is no significant effect of Emotional domestic violence on academic performance of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt metropolis.

METHODOLOGY

Expos Facto or Causal Comparative research design was adopted for the study. The population of this study consists of six thousand eight hundred and two (6,802) senior secondary students in Port Harcourt metropolis, multi-stage sampling procedure was used to sample 378 students from the population using Taro Yemen formula. However, out of 378 instruments distributed to the sampled teachers, 271 were properly filled which was collated and used for data analysis. Data were collected using three adapted instruments, the first instrument was titled "Academic Performance Scale (APS), the second were titled "Physical Domestic Violence (PDVS) and the third instrument was titled "Emotional Domestic Violence Scale (EDVS). The instruments were validated by experts from measurement and evaluation, department of educational psychology guidance and counselling. Construct validity of the instrument was determined through factor analysis. Cronbach Alpha method was used by the researcher for the determination of the reliability of the internal consistency of the instrument. Twenty (20) copies of the instruments were administered to Teachers outside the study sample. Data gotten from this were analyzed using Cronbach Alpha statistics and reliability coefficients were determined as 0.75, 0.68 and 0.89 for Academic Performance, Physical Domestic Violence and Emotional Domestic Violence respectively. Simple regression analysis was used to answer all the research questions. T-test associated with simple regression was used to test the corresponding hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *What is the effect of Physical domestic violence on academic performance of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Metropolis?*

Table 1: Simple Regression Showing the Effect of Physical Domestic Violence on Academic Performance of Senior Secondary School Students

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square
.44 ^a	.726	.821

Table 1 showed R-value is .44, R²-value is .726 and adjusted R² is .821. This suggests that approximately 72.6% of the variance in academic performance can be explained by physical domestic violence female students. This implies that physical domestic violence to a very high extent affects academic performance of senior secondary school students

Hypothesis One: There is no significant effect of Physical domestic violence on academic performance of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Metropolis

Table 2: T-test associated with simple Regressions of the Effect of Physical Domestic Violence on Academic Performance of Senior Secondary School Students

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta				B
1	(Constant)	28.743	1.415		20.317	.047	25.960	31.525
	Academic Performance	-.096	.048	-.106	-1.996	.000	-.190	-.001

Table 2 showed that β – value is -106 and P-vale is .000. Since the P-vale is less than .05, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate sustain, therefore there is significant effect of physical domestic violence on academic performance of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Research Question Two: *What is the effect of Emotional domestic violence on academic performance of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt metropolis?*

Table 3: Simple Regression Showing the Effect of Emotional Domestic Violence on Academic Performance of Senior Secondary School Students

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square
.044 ^a	.623	.731

Table 3 showed R-value is .044, R²-value is .623 and adjusted R² is .623. This suggests that approximately 62.3% of the variance in academic performance can be explained emotional domestic violence of female students. This implies that emotional domestic violence to a very high extent affects academic performance of senior secondary school students

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant effect of Emotional domestic violence on academic performance of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt metropolis.

Table 4: T-test associated with simple Regressions of the Effect of Emotioanl Domestic Violence on Academic Performance of Senior Secondary School Students

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta				B
1	(Constant)	27.720	1.372		20.200	.405	25.021	30.419
	Academic Performance	.042	.050	.044	.833	.000	-.057	.141

Table 4 showed that β – value is .044 and P-value is .000. Since the P-value is less than .05, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate sustain, therefore there is no significant effect of Emotional domestic violence on academic performance of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt metropolis.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Effect of Physical Domestic Violence on Academic Performance of Students

The findings of this study demonstrate that physical domestic violence significantly and negatively affects the academic performance of secondary school students. This suggests that physical domestic violence is a major predictor of academic outcomes among the students, highlighting the severity of its educational consequences. This finding is strongly supported by recent empirical studies which have established that children and adolescents exposed to domestic violence often experience learning difficulties, reduced concentration, poor classroom engagement, absenteeism, and declining academic achievement. Vachon et al. (2020) supported this finding that exposure to family violence significantly disrupts cognitive functioning and emotional stability, both of which are critical for academic success. Similarly, Bentil et al. (2024) supported this finding by reporting that secondary school students exposed to physical violence at home consistently performed below their peers academically due to stress, fear, and emotional exhaustion. From a psychological standpoint, the negative effect observed in this study aligns with trauma and stress theories, which explain that repeated exposure to violence activates chronic stress responses that impair attention, memory, and executive functioning. These impairments reduce students' ability to process information, complete academic tasks, and perform well in examinations (Lagdon et al., 2021). Despite the strong support for the present findings, some scholars have reported more nuanced outcomes. For instance, Archer and Graham-Kevan (2020) argue against the findings that while domestic violence generally has negative effects on academic outcomes, the magnitude of the effect may vary depending on moderating factors such as resilience, social support, school climate, and access to counselling services. In some contexts, students exposed to violence may still maintain average academic performance due to strong teacher support or adaptive coping strategies. Additionally, a few studies suggest that emotional and psychological abuse may sometimes exert stronger long-term academic effects than physical violence, as physical abuse may be more visible and attract quicker intervention (Dokkedahl et al., 2019). However, these perspectives do not negate the present findings; rather, they suggest that physical domestic violence interacts with other psychosocial variables that may either amplify or reduce its impact on academic performance.

Effect of Emotional Domestic Violence on Academic Performance of Students

The findings of this study demonstrate that emotional domestic violence significantly and positively affects the academic performance of secondary school students. This suggests that emotional domestic violence constitutes an important contextual factor influencing students' academic experiences and outcomes. In theory, this implies that persistent exposure to emotional abuse—such as humiliation, verbal threats, emotional neglect, and psychological manipulation—may substantially undermine students' cognitive, emotional, and motivational capacities required for effective learning. This result is consistent with several empirical studies which emphasize that emotional domestic violence exerts profound effects on adolescents' psychological functioning, school engagement, and academic outcomes. Dokkedahl et al. (2019) supported this finding by arguing that emotional abuse is often more damaging than physical abuse because it directly attacks victims' self-esteem, emotional stability, and sense of safety, which are foundational for academic success. Similarly, Lagdon et al. (2021) reported that prolonged emotional victimization is strongly associated with concentration difficulties, anxiety, depressive symptoms, and reduced academic motivation among adolescents. Again, Fry et al. (2020) observed that emotional abuse impacts academic outcomes primarily through mediating variables such as emotional regulation difficulties, low self-esteem, anxiety, and school disengagement. When these mediating factors are not explicitly modeled, the direct effect of emotional violence may appear statistically weak or inconsistent.

A longitudinal study by Kim and Leventhal (2021) found that while emotional abuse significantly predicted emotional distress and behavioral problems, its direct association with academic achievement diminished when psychosocial variables such as resilience and peer support were controlled. This suggests that emotional domestic violence may influence academic performance indirectly through psychological and emotional pathways, rather than through immediate academic disruption.

In contrast, other scholars argue that emotional domestic violence has a strong and direct negative effect on academic performance. For instance, Vachon et al. (2020) found that emotional maltreatment was a significant predictor of reduced academic achievement, even after controlling for socioeconomic status and physical abuse. Likewise, Sardinha et al. (2022) emphasized that emotional violence against girls contributes to chronic stress and learned helplessness, which directly impair academic persistence and performance. The contradiction between these findings and the present study may be attributed to contextual differences, measurement approaches, cultural norms, and coping mechanisms. In some cultural settings, emotional abuse may be normalized, reducing its observable direct impact on academic outcomes, even though its psychological effects remain substantial (Archer & Graham-Kevan, 2020).

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study clearly indicate that domestic violence, in both its physical and emotional forms, is a critical factor that affects the academic performance of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The study concludes that physical domestic violence exerts a more direct and severe influence on academic performance, whereas emotional domestic violence operates more subtly and indirectly. Both forms of domestic violence, however, undermine students' holistic development and academic success.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made;

1. School authorities should strengthen guidance and counselling services to identify and support students exposed to domestic violence.
2. Parents and guardians should be sensitised through community programmes on the negative educational consequences of physical and emotional domestic violence.
3. Government and non-governmental organisations should implement child-protection and family-support initiatives aimed at reducing domestic violence and promoting students' academic well-being.

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